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Effects of Extruded Linseed on Ruminal Fermentation, Rumen Microbiota, and Enteric Methane Emissions in Lactating Dairy Cows Fed Corn- or Grass-Silage-Based Diets

J. Van Mullem,^{1,2}

¹Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), 9090 Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium

²Department of Animal Sciences and Aquatic Ecology, Ghent University, 9000 Ghent, Belgium

ABSTRACT

Extruded linseed (EL) supplementation is a recognized strategy to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions in dairy cows, although its mitigation potential may depend on diet composition. This study evaluated the impact of EL on production performance, CH₄ emissions, ruminal fermentation and microbiota in corn silage (CS)- and grass silage (GS)-based diet. Forty lactating Holstein–Friesian cows (99 ± 41 DIM, 34.7 ± 5.2 kg milk, and mean parity of 3.2 ± 1.9) were used in an incomplete Latin square design with a 2 × 2 factorial arrangement: CS– (CS:GS = 75:25) or GS– (CS:GS = 25:75) based diet, with (EL) or without EL supplementation (CTRL) providing 400 g crude fat/d. Each period lasted 35 d Dry matter intake (Roughage Intake Control bins), milk yield and composition, and CH₄ emissions (GreenFeed) were measured during the last 3 weeks of each period. Rumen samples were collected for VFA analysis and metataxonomic profiling of bacteria, archaea, protozoa, and fungi. No interaction between EL supplementation and diet composition was observed. Compared with the CS-based diet, the GS-based diet increased CH₄ production, yield, and intensity by 5%, 6%, and 8%, respectively. Milk production and fat- and protein corrected milk (FPCM) were on average 2.1 kg/d and 1.8 kg/d lower in cows fed the GS-based diet compared with the CS-based diet. The fermentation pattern shifted, with higher proportions of acetate (+1.4 μmol/mol), butyrate (+1.1 mmol/mol), and lower propionate proportion (−0.06 mmol/mol) in cows fed the GS-based diets compared with the CS-based diet. Alpha diversity of bacteria, fungi, and protozoa was higher in GS-based diet compared with the CS-based diet. Across diets, supplementation of EL reduced CH₄ production and intensity by 5% and 8% respectively. Al-

though β diversity of bacterial and archaeal communities was affected, only minor compositional changes were detected. EL supplementation numerically increased net energy intake, resulting in a higher milk yield (+1.1 kg/d) compared with CTRL. At the applied inclusion level, CH₄ mitigation by EL was mainly the result of a reduced fermentable OM intake, rather than a shift in fermentation pattern or rumen microbiota.

Key words: dietary lipids, greenhouse gases, lactation, dietary strategy

INTRODUCTION

The rumen microbiota play a vital role by producing metabolic substrates that provide nearly 70% of the energy required for the ruminant to sustain physiological functions (Liu et al., 2023). However, during ruminal fermentation, byproducts such as H₂ and CO₂ are also produced and subsequently converted into CH₄ by methanogenic archaea, representing a negative side effect (Russell and Hespell, 1981; Janssen, 2010; Pereira et al., 2022). Enteric fermentation, mainly from cattle, and manure management, account for about 33% of global anthropogenic CH₄ emissions (FAOSTAT, 2025) and has a global warming potential of 27 times that of CO₂ over a 100 yr period (IPCC, 2021). Due to its short lifespan of 12 yr, reducing global CH₄ emissions offers short-term climate benefits, making the mitigation of enteric emissions a key priority (Lynch et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021). In parallel with efforts to reduce the climate impact of livestock, there is growing encouragement to make greater use of grass-based feed sources, such as grass silage (GS). Policy frameworks such as the Common Agricultural Policy and the European Green Deal promote the use of grassland products, recognizing the important ecosystem services that grasslands provide, including biodiversity support and carbon (C) sequestration (Bengtsson et al., 2019). Roughages play an important role in dairy cattle diets and are often a combination of GS and CS in varying proportions (Hassanat

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*Corresponding author: Tel: +3292722626, EM: Leen.vandaele@ilvo.vlaanderen.be, Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 119, 9090 Merelbeke-Melle, Belgium

The list of standard abbreviations for JDS is available at adsa.org/jds-abbreviations-26. Nonstandard abbreviations are available in the Notes.

et al., 2013; van Gastelen et al., 2015; Van Wesemael, 2019). While grass silage (GS) production is generally associated with higher N inputs and greater risks of N losses to the environment (e.g., NH_3 volatilization, N_2O emissions, and NO_3 leaching) (van Groenigen et al., 2004; Mogensen et al., 2014), perennial grasslands can enhance soil C sequestration and typically require less intensive soil disturbance, thereby reducing CO_2 emissions related to ploughing and field operations (Vellinga et al., 2004; Mogensen et al., 2014). Additionally, lower protein content in (non-supplemented) CS-based diets, results in higher needs for protein rich concentrates such as soybean meal, also associated with high GHG-emission (Brask-Pedersen et al., 2023). Furthermore, Diets based on GS are generally associated with higher NDF concentrations, whereas diets based on CS typically contain greater amounts of starch (Dijkstra et al., 2016; van Gastelen et al., 2023). However, a potential conflict arises between the goals of reducing CH_4 emissions and increased use of GS. First, the exchange of corn silage (CS) for GS in ruminant diets has been associated with increased enteric CH_4 emissions (van Gastelen et al., 2015), as the higher NDF and lower starch content is associated with a shift toward an increased acetate proportion and reduced propionate proportion (Bannink et al., 2008). Furthermore, GS has a higher degradability compared with CS, also resulting in more substrate for CH_4 production (van Gastelen et al., 2015). Moreover, there are indications that nutritional CH_4 mitigation strategies may exhibit a reduced reduction potential when added to diets with a higher proportion of GS. For example, the effectiveness of 3-NOP in reducing CH_4 yield (g/kg DMI) has been shown to depend on the diet's NDF and starch content, with higher NDF and lower starch levels being associated with reduced 3-NOP efficacy (Kebreab et al., 2023). But also in other mitigation strategies, a diet dependency could be expected. In a previous study, supplementation with extruded linseed (EL) in a CS-based diet significantly reduced CH_4 yield. However, when the same amount of EL was added to a GS-based diet in a second experiment, no significant reduction in CH_4 yield was observed (Van Mullem et al., 2025). This interaction may stem from the fact that both EL supplementation and dietary replacement of CS by GS or vice versa affect the microbial community, potentially in antagonistic ways with consequences for the CH_4 emissions. Supplementation with EL increases the dietary intake of PUFA, which are known to exert toxic effects on cellulolytic bacteria and protozoa in the rumen (Jenkins, 1993; Martin et al., 2016). This microbial disruption can lead to shifts in VFA profiles, typically resulting in higher proportions of propionate (Johnson and Johnson, 1995; Beauchemin et al., 2022). Similarly, the composition of the rumen microbiota is strongly influenced by diet (Henderson et al.,

2015; Newbold and Ramos-Morales, 2020), with increasing levels of starch promoting propionate production (Janssen, 2010). Propionate formation acts as an alternative H_2 sink, creating a more H_2 -limited environment and thereby a smaller methanogenic substrate pool (Janssen, 2010; Ungerfeld, 2020). As such, EL supplementation may reduce a larger fraction of the total methanogenic potential in a CS-based diet, as also suggested for other CH_4 -mitigating strategies (Kebreab et al., 2023, 2025). Furthermore, starch-rich diets have been associated with reduced microbial richness (Belanche et al., 2012), which could compromise the microbial functionality and resilience (Palmonari et al., 2024). This suggests that the CS diet may be more sensitive to perturbations in the rumen microbiota, resulting in an increased effect of EL supplementation on CH_4 emissions. In addition, dietary lipids may reduce digestibility by coating structural carbohydrates, thereby limiting microbial access (Jenkins, 1993; Ellis et al., 2008). Given that CS is richer in starch (Vaidya et al., 2020), this coating effect may be less pronounced in CS-based diets. Together, these differences in microbial composition and substrate accessibility could modulate the response to EL, leading to variable fermentation outcomes. However, evidence on the effects of EL on ruminal microbial communities remains scarce (Veneman et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2016; Popova et al., 2019) and, to our knowledge, is lacking in the context of different dietary backgrounds. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to: (1) evaluate the potential of EL to reduce CH_4 emissions and determine whether this reduction is affected by its combination with a CS- or GS-based diet; and (2) examine the impact of EL on rumen microbial communities, including bacteria, archaea, fungi, and protozoa, and assess potential interactions when combined with either a CS- or GS-based diet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical statement

All experimental procedures were approved by the ILVO Animal Ethics Committee (EC 2023/451).

Experimental design

The trial included 40 cows and was conducted as an incomplete 4×3 Latin square (balanced crossover) with 4 dietary treatments arranged in a 2×2 factorial design, including 2 diets and 2 treatments applied over 3 periods of 5 wk each. Two experimental partial mixed rations (PMR) were formulated: a CS-based diet and a GS-based diet. Each PMR was supplemented with concentrates that did not or did include an extruded linseed (EL) product (*Linex Pure*, Arvesta), resulting in 4 dietary treatments:

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the experimental design. All cows ($n = 40$) were housed together during the whole trial. For each animal, the trial consisted of a pre-experimental period of 3 weeks (W-2 – W0) and 3 treatment periods of 5 weeks each. Each treatment period consisted of 21 d of adaptation (weeks colored in gray) and 14 d of data collection (weeks shown in bold). In wk 4, 9 and 14, rumen samples (R) were taken, and in wk 5, 10 and 15, milk samples were taken. Each cow was assigned to a sequence of 3 treatments including: 1) CS CTRL, 2) CS EL, 3) GS CTRL, and 4) GS EL. The CS diets consisted of a PMR with CS:GS of 75:25 and the GS diet consisted of a PMR with CS:GS of 25:75. In the EL treatments, 3 kg DM day⁻¹ balanced concentrates were iso-energetically replaced with 1.9 kg DM day⁻¹ EL product (Linex Pure, Arvesta, Belgium).

1) CS-CTRL: a CS-based diet (25% GS and 75% CS), 2) CS-EL: the CS-CTRL diet in which a part of the balanced concentrate was replaced with EL, 3) GS-CTRL: a GS-based diet (75% GS and 25% CS) and 4) GS-EL: the GS-CTRL diet in which a part of the balanced concentrate was replaced with EL. The animal trial lasted for 119 d and was divided into a pre-experimental period of 14 d (without data collection) and 3 treatment periods of 35d. Each cow represented one experimental unit. Animals were randomly assigned to one of 24 unique treatment sequences (ABC, ABD, ACB, ACD, ADB, ADC, BAC, BAD, BCA, BCD, BDA, BDC, CAB, CAD, CBA, CBD, CDA, CDB, DAB, DAC, DBA, DBC, DCA, DCB), with each letter representing a specific treatment in a given experimental period. Subsequently, the dietary treatments were randomly assigned to the letters A, B, C, and D. This allocation was performed before the start of the first treatment period. A schematic overview of the experimental design is provided in Figure 1.

Animals and housing

The experiment included 40 lactating Holstein Friesian cows (14 primiparous, 26 multiparous) with average \pm SD values at the start of the first experimental period of 99 ± 41 DIM, 34.7 ± 5.2 kg milk yield/d, 3.2 ± 1.9 lactations, and 663 ± 73 kg of BW. Throughout the whole study, animals were housed in a free-stall barn with cubicles. Beforehand, no criteria to include or exclude animals were established. However, one multiparous cow was removed from the trial due to persistent stealing behavior, and data from 2 additional multiparous cows were excluded due to unreliable feed intake measurements. In the end, data of 37 cows were retained for data analysis.

Diets and treatments

The ingredient and chemical composition of the total diet (PMR + concentrates fed in the automated concen-

trate feeder and in the GreenFeed) of the 4 treatments fed during the experiment is shown in Table 1. Chemical composition of each feed ingredient is shown in Supplementary table S1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18797675>). Both PMR were formulated to be isoenergetic and remained the same throughout the study. The GS-based PMR aimed for a starch content of 16% and consisted of 59% pre-wilted grass silage, 19% corn silage, 9% pressed beet pulp, 10% balanced concentrate, and 4% corn meal on DM basis. The CS-based PMR targeted a starch content of 20% and was composed of 63% CS, 21% pre-wilted GS, 10% pressed beet pulp, 6% soybean meal, and 1% wheat urea on DM basis. Starting from an ad libitum intake of the PMR, cows were further supplemented with concentrates (balanced concentrate and heat-treated soybean meal) in automatic feeders (Delaval NV) to fulfill 105% of the individual requirements for NE_L and MP. The automatic concentrate feeder operates on a savings-based allocation system. Each cow is assigned a fixed daily amount of concentrate, which is released in small portions every hour throughout the day. A minimum and maximum amount can be dispensed per visit to regulate intake. If a cow does not collect her full daily allocation, she is allowed to carry over a limited proportion (up to half) to the following day. Unused amounts cannot accumulate beyond this limit. When cows were allocated to an EL treatment, 3.0 kg DM of balanced concentrate in the automatic concentrate feeders was replaced by 1.9 kg DM of EL product (Linex, Arvesta NV; with main ingredients including 39% EL, 19% wheat, 19% sunflower meal, and 8% steam-flaked corn) to provide 400 g crude fat and 200 g α -linolenic acid per d (on DM basis, Supplementary Table S2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18797643>), and was based on its practical feasibility for farmers. The amount of concentrates was determined based on individual requirements for MP (Tamminga et al., 1994) and NE_L (Van Es, 1978) and taken into account the DMI of the PMR at the start of the trial, milk yield and parity. Adjustments to

concentrate intake were made throughout the experiment in accordance with the progression of the lactation curve. In the second (wk 2, wk 7, wk 12) and the fourth wk (wk 4, wk 9, and wk 14) of each treatment period, the concentrate allowance was reduced by 200 g. These adjustments were the same for each cow and irrespective of the diet or treatment. The NE_L and MP contents of feed ingredients and were calculated based on the Dutch feed evaluation system (Van Es, 1978; Tamminga et al., 1994) and based on pre-trial chemical analysis of the feed ingredients.

Measurements

Each cow had free access to the PMR corresponding to its assigned treatment and PMR was offered 3 times daily (7:00 a.m.; 1:00 p.m. and 6:00 p.m.) in 20 Roughage Intake Control feed (RIC) bins (Hokofarm Group). Each diet was assigned to 10 Roughage Intake Control bins. At the start of every experimental period, cows were then allocated to the RIC bins corresponding to their allocated diet. Concentrates and the EL product were administered throughout the day at automated feed stations (Delaval NV) located in the free-stall and in the milking parlor. The RIC bins and the feed stations registered individual daily feed intake of each cow. Feed samples were taken every 2 wk at one time point, except for the pre-wilted GS, which was sampled at 2 time points every wk. Feed samples were pooled per period for pre-wilted GS and CS or over the whole study for all other feed ingredients. Cows were milked twice daily at 6 a.m. and 5 p.m. in a herringbone milking parlor. Milk production was registered automatically (Delpro Farm Manager, Delaval NV). Milk samples were collected during 4 consecutive milkings in the last wk of each treatment period (wk 5, 10, and 15) of the experiment. Milk samples were analyzed for protein, fat, lactose and urea content using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (Lactoscope FTA-3.X, PerkinElmer). Fat and protein corrected milk (FPCM) was calculated using the following formula: FPCM yield = milk production \times [0.337 + (0.116 \times milk fat %) + (0.06 \times milk protein %)] (Subnel et al., 1994). Individual BW (scale, DeLaval NV) was measured after each milking.

Methane emissions

Enteric CH_4 was measured daily using a GreenFeed system (C-Lock Inc.) placed in the free-stall. One GreenFeed unit was used and all cows had continuous access based on a voluntary feeding schedule, similar as in Van Wesemael et al., (2019) and Van De Gucht et al. (2025). In this schedule, cows were intended to receive 1 kg of balanced concentrate, dispensed as 24 drops of 43 g each over 4 visits (6 drops/visit) at 30-s intervals, with a minimum of 6 h between 2 visits. The GreenFeed gas

sensors were calibrated automatically on a daily basis and the airflow sensor was calibrated at the start of the first treatment period, and alternating every 2 and every 3 weeks (wk 2, wk 5, wk 7, wk 10, wk 12 and wk 15). The concentrate used as bait in the Greenfeed was a mixture of balanced concentrate and balanced concentrate rich in starch. For data analysis, only measurements from the last 3 wk of the treatment period were used. Data were retained only for animals with at least 21 successful measurements and a minimum airflow of 26 L/s. In total, 11 cowperiod means were excluded because the number of good visits was below 21: 6 in the first treatment period, 3 in the second, and 2 in the third. Cows had on average (\pm SD) 2.14 (\pm 0.56) successful measurements/d. concentrate DMI from bait used in the greenfeed was 0.5, 0.6, 0.6, and 0.6 kg/d for CS CTRL, CS EL, GS CTRL, and GS EL. Enteric CH_4 emissions were expressed as absolute CH_4 emissions (g CH_4 /d), CH_4 yield (g CH_4 /kg DMI), CH_4 intensity (g CH_4 /kg milk and g CH_4 /kg FPCM).

Rumen sampling

Rumen samples were collected in wk 4 of each treatment period (wk 4, 9, and 14 of the experiment). Sampling was conducted at 8:00 a.m., before the morning feeding and after morning milking, using a rumen flora scoop (Vuxxx). To minimize the time without feed access, cows were divided into 2 equal groups, with sampling carried out over 2 consecutive days, ensuring that each animal was sampled once per period. The group assignments remained unchanged throughout the trial, and each group was sampled on the same day in each period. The flora scoop was inserted through the mouth and esophagus into the rumen to collect approximately 60 mL of rumen contents, consisting of fluid and small feed particles (<10 mm), as described by Geishauser et al. (2012). If sampling failed after 2 attempts, the procedure was stopped. Using a blunt-ended pipette tip, 1.5 mL subsamples were aliquoted into cryovials, snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80°C for microbial analysis. The remaining rumen contents were collected in a small container, the pH was measured (testo 206-pH1, Testo SE & Co KGaA.), and the sample was stored at -20°C for VFA analysis.

Chemical analysis and feed evaluation

Feed samples were analyzed as described in De Boever (2017). First, samples of roughage ingredients were dried in a ventilated oven at 65°C and ground using a 1mm screen (Rheotec). For the determination of residual moisture content, subsamples of all feed ingredients were dried at 103°C (EC, 2009) followed by incineration

Table 1. Ingredients and chemical composition¹ of the total diets (PMR + concentrates)

	Dietary treatments ²			
	CS		GS	
	CTRL	EL	CTRL	EL
Ingredients of the diet (g/kg DM)				
Corn silage	479	506	180	191
Prewilted grass silage	157	162	426	433
Pressed beet pulp	62	65	59	61
Corn meal			28	29
Soybean meal	64	68	4	5
Treated soybean meal ³	9	8	10	9
Balanced concentrates	166	45	190	71
Balanced concentrates starch	37	32	79	82
GreenFeed bait ⁴	22	25	24	29
Extruded linseed product		83		88
Urea mix ⁵	7	8		
Chemical composition of the total diet (g/kg DM unless stated otherwise)				
DM (g/kg)	456	445	466	459
CP	150	148	138	140
Crude ash	65	58	80	74
Crude fat	26	40	27	42
Crude fiber	188	192	202	204
NDF	341	345	357	357
Starch	213	209	160	155
Sugar	37	34	49	47
NE _L ⁶	6.71	7.06	6.71	7.00
MP ⁷	91.8	98.0	85.0	92.1
RDPB ⁸	1.3	-1.8	-1.5	-4.6
FOM	582	564	589	571

¹Chemical composition was calculated based on the average intake of the cows, during 14d of data collection in the treatment periods.

²Different dietary treatments with PMR: CS = corn silage-based diet (CS:GS of 75:25), GS = grass silage-based diet (CS:GS of 25:75), and treatments within each diet: CTRL = control treatment, EL = EL replacing a part of the balanced concentrates from the CTRL treatment.

³Heat treated soybean meal.

⁴GreenFeed bait was formulated with a composition of 50% balanced concentrate blend and 50% starch-based concentrate.

⁵15% rolled barley and 85% urea.

⁶Net energy for lactation, Van Es, 1978.

⁷Metabolizable protein, Tamminga et al., 1994.

⁸Rumen degradable protein balance, Tamminga et al., 1994.

at 550°C to determine the crude ash content (ISO:5984, 2022). Kjeldahl was used to determine the CP ($N \times 6.25$) content (ISO:5983-2, 2005). Petroleum ether was used to extract crude fat after hydrolyzing with hydrochloric acid (ISO: 6492, 1992). Crude fiber was obtained by the Ankom Fiber Analyzer (AnkomTechnology, USA) after boiling with sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide (EC, 1992). Next, NDF (all feed ingredients) and ADF (roughage feed ingredients) were determined with the Ankom Fiber Analyzer. The NDF content was obtained using α -amylase and sodium sulphite and expressed on ash-free basis (Van Soest et al., 1991). After drying and weighing, the residue was treated with sulphuric acid to determine ADL (roughage feed ingredients). Then, ADF and ADL were corrected for ash in the ADL residue (Van Soest et al., 1991). Starch was determined after autoclaving and

hydrolysis with amyloglucosidase (NEN, 1974). Sugars were extracted with 40% ethanol and analyzed according to the Luff-Schoorl method (EC, 1971). The fermentation products were determined from a water extract: lactic acid was measured using an enzymatic method (Noll, 1966), while acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid, and alcohols were analyzed by GC (Varian 3900) as described by Jouany (1981). Chromatographic analysis was performed using a DB-Fatwax UI column (30 m length, 0.25 mm internal diameter, 0.25 μ m film thickness). The injector was maintained at 200°C with a split ratio of 2, and the flame ionization detector (FID) was set at 250°C. A 10 μ L injection volume of each sample was employed for all analyses. The oven of the column start at 40°C and goes stepwise to 230°C. In addition, pH and the proportion of ammonia N (% NH_3 -N/total N) were

determined according to ISO 5983–2 (2005). The DM content and the chemical composition of the silages were corrected for losses of volatile substances during drying (Dulphy and Demarquilly, 1981). Rumen fermentability of OM, MP and RDP balance (**RDPB**) were estimated using the degradation characteristics of the nutrients based on the Dutch protein evaluation system (Tamminga et al., 1994). The NE_L of the feeds was predicted with regression equations based on chemical composition and in vitro OM degradability (De Boever et al., 1999) using cellulase (De Boever et al., 1988). The NE_L , MP, and RDPB for the EL product, values were delivered by the manufacturer (Arvesta). The acid insoluble ash content was determined in all oven-dried (65°C) and ground (1mm screen, Whiley, Rheotec) feed ingredients following ISO 5985 (2022).

The determination of the fatty acids (**FA**) in the feed components was performed as described by Vlaeminck et al. (2014), FA methyl esters were prepared by transesterification using NaOH/MeOH followed by HCl/MeOH and subsequently analyzed by GC (HP 7890A, Agilent Technologies). Separation was carried out on a fused silica SP-2560 capillary column (75 m × 0.18 mm i.d. × 0.14 µm film thickness; Supelco Analytical) with a flame ionization detector. For each sample type, an appropriate injection volume of the FA methyl esters solution was used. H₂ was employed as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. Individual peaks were identified by comparison with retention times of reference standards (GLC463, Nu-Chek-Prep). Quantification was performed using nonadecanoic acid (C19:0) as the internal standard.

The nutrient concentrations obtained from the chemical analyses were subsequently used to estimate the gross energy (**GE**) content of the feeds. The GE content (MJ/kg DM) was calculated according to the following equation (Van Es, 1978):

$$GE_{\text{feed}} = 0.02414 \times \text{CP} + 0.03657 \times \text{crude fat} + 0.02092 \times \text{crude fiber} + 0.01699 \times \text{NFC} - 0.00063 \times \text{sugar}.$$

The calculated GE_{feed} was then multiplied by the DMI (kg/d) to obtain the GE intake (GEI, MJ/d).

Analysis of VFA in rumen fluid was performed as described in Castro-Montoya et al., (2012), a 1 mL aliquot of rumen fluid was transferred into a 2 mL vial. An internal standard solution consisting of 2-ethylbutyric acid dissolved in formic acid (10 mg/mL) was added (100 µL). After centrifugation at 22,808 g for 15 min at 4 °C, VFA in the supernatant were quantified using GC (HP 7890A, Agilent Technologies).

DNA extraction and sequencing

DNA was extracted from 1 mL of rumen fluid using the DNeasy Powersoil Pro Kit (Qiagen) following the instructions of the manufacturer. DNA concentration and purity were assessed by measuring absorbance ratios at 260 nm/280 nm (A260/280) and 260 nm/230 nm using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) before being stored at –20°C. The extracted DNA was sent to Edinburgh Genetics (Midlothian) for the amplicon sequencing. Amplicon sequencing was performed for all 4 microbial groups: bacteria, archaea, protozoa and fungi. The primers used for library preparation are shown in Table 2. The sequencing was carried out by using the Illumina MiSeq V3-technology (2 × 250 bp). The sequence was demultiplexed and the barcodes were cut off by the company. The raw sequence data are stored in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI: PRJNA1210510).

Quantitative PCR analysis

Quantitative PCR analysis was used to quantify the total amount of bacteria, archaea, fungi, and protozoa. Primers used for amplification are shown in Table 2. The qPCR analysis was performed with a StepOne Real Time PCR system (ThermoFisher scientific) using V2.3 software. For the quantitative PCR, volumes of 12.5 µL containing 2 µL of extracted DNA with a concentration of 20 ng/µL, 1 µL of primer mixture containing a forward and a reverse primer (0.5 µM), 6.25 µL of maxima SYBR Green/Rox quantitative PCR mastermix (ThermoFisher scientific), and was further diluted with 3.25 µL nuclease-free water. Amplification of each target group was carried out in a 2-step cycling protocol (StepOne Real Time PCR System, Applied Biosystems) with the following program: initial denaturation at 95°C for 10 min, 35 cycles at 95°C for 15 s (denaturation), 60°C for 1 min for annealing and extension. The melting curve was built by measuring fluorescence emissions with increased temperature from 60 to 95°C with ramps of 0.5°C every 15 s. A plasmid containing a single copy of the targeted gene was used as qPCR standard. The copy numbers in the standards were calculated based on the DNA concentrations determined by the NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). External standards were prepared and used in every qPCR run to enumerate the gene copies in the samples. The absolute quantity of each group of microorganisms was calculated using the respective standards and expressed as corresponding gene copies per milliliter of sample. In each run, DNA standard series were used to generate calibration curves and subsequently to calculate the absolute quantity in the DNA samples.

Microbial data analysis

The raw sequencing data were processed using the QIIME 2 pipeline (version 2023.5.1-foss-2022a) (Bolyen et al., 2019). Initially, a visual quality assessment of the demultiplexed reads was performed. Denoising and chimera removal were conducted using the DADA2 plugin. During this step, primer sequences were trimmed, and reads were truncated to 250 base pairs (forward) and 210 base pairs (reverse). For protozoan sequences, both forward and reverse reads were truncated to 249 base pairs. This process produced a feature table representing amplicon sequence variants (ASV). The feature table was subsequently summarized, and low-abundance features were filtered by retaining only those present at a minimum frequency of 2 and in at least 2 samples, similar as in Yang et al. (2022). A phylogenetic tree was then constructed to support downstream diversity analyses. Taxonomic classification of denoised sequences was performed using the feature-classifier classify-sklearn method with specific pre-trained classifiers. The greengenes2 (version 2022.10 (McDonald et al., 2024)) database was used for bacteria and archaea. The fungal classifier was constructed using the sequences released under anaerobic fungi D1/D2_LSU database (<https://anaerobicfungi.org/databases/>; version 2.0). For protozoa, a classifier was constructed using the sequences in Ci_seqs_2015.fasta (Kittelmann et al., 2015). Subsequent ecological and statistical analyses were conducted in RStudio (version, 4.4.2, www.r-project.org). The filtered feature table, phylogenetic tree, and taxonomy assignments were imported into R using the phyloseq package (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). Taxonomic classification of reads was performed across multiple hierarchical levels, including phylum, class, order, family, and genus. To assess sequencing depth and coverage, rarefaction analysis was conducted using the vegan package (Oksanen et al., 2025). The resulting rarefaction curves (see Supplementary Figure S1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17596859>) showed a clear plateau, indicating that sufficient sequencing depth had been achieved and that the majority of microbial diversity had been captured (Zaheer et al., 2018). Analysis was performed separately between bacteria, archaea, fungi and protozoa. Alpha diversity measures (Observed ASV, Shannon index, and Simpson index), describing the amount of differentiation within samples, were measured in rarefied data using the “Phyloseq” package (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). These measures were further analyzed using a general linear mixed effect model using the “lme4” package, with the model including diet, treatment, their interaction, and period as fixed effects and cow as random effects using a gamma distribution with a log link function. Pairwise comparisons (diet x treatment) were conducted using the “emmeans” package

Table 2. Overview of the primers used for library preparation and quantitative PCR analysis

Target group	Gene region	Library preparation primers			Reference
		Primer name	Primer Sequence	Base pairs	
Bacteria	16S rRNA (V4)	515F	GTGCCAGMCGCCGGTAA	Caporaso et al., 2011	
		806R	GACTACHVGGGTATCTAAT		
		349F	GYCASCAGKCGMGAAW		
		806R	GGACTACVSGGTATCTAAT		
Archaea	16S rRNA (V3-V4)	AGF-LSU-EnVs D1	CGGTTTRCACCASGTGTGTT	Takai and Horikoshi, 2000	
		AGF-LSU-EnVs D2	GTC AACATCCTAAGYTAGGTA		
Fungi	LSU rRNA (D1-D2)	P-SSU-316F	GC TTTCGWTGGTAGTGAT	Young et al., 2022	
Protozoa	18S rRNA (V3-V4)	GIC758R	CAACTGTCTCTATKAAAYCG	Ishaq and Wright, 2014	
		Quantitative PCR primers			
Bacteria	Glycerol 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (G3P)	Primer name	Primer sequence	Reference	
		Gbacteria_F	CGGCAACGAGCGCAACCC	Denman and McSweeney, 2006	
Archaea	16S rRNA (V3-V4)	Gbacteria_R	CCATTGTAGCACGTGTGTAGCC	Skillman et al., 2004; Watanabe et al., 2004	
		915af	AGGAATGGCGGGGAGCAC		
Fungi	18S rRNA (V3-V4)	1386r	GCGGTGTGTCAAGGAGC	Edwards et al., 2008	
		Neo QPCR F	TTGACAATGGATCTCTGGTTCTC	Carberry et al., 2012	
Protozoa	18S rRNA (V3-V4)	Neo QPCR R	GTGCAATATGCGTTTCGAAAGATT		
		316F	GC TTTCGWTGGTAGTGAT		
		539R	CTTGCCCTCYAATCGTWTCT		

(Lenth, 2017), applying a Sidak correction for multiple comparisons. Beta-diversity, describing the amount of differentiation between samples, was assessed with the Bray Curtis dissimilarity and visualized using the non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) method. Read counts were transformed into relative abundances. Statistical differences between communities were analyzed using permutational multivariate ANOVA (PERMANOVA) using the `adonis2` function from the “vegan” package (Oksanen et al., 2025). The model used in this analysis included diet, treatment, period and cow as explanatory variables. Differential abundance analysis between diet, treatment and their interaction was performed using DESeq2 package with a Wald test on genus level. Log₂ fold changes (**Log₂FC**), indicating the magnitude and direction of abundance differences, were shrunk using the `apeglm` method, and genera with an adjusted *p*-value < 0.05 were considered significant (Zhu et al., 2019). Before this differential abundance analysis, ASV were filtered by retaining only those with at least 10 reads in a minimum of 3 samples to exclude low-abundance and rare features likely resulting from sequencing noise. After preprocessing and quality filtering, sequencing of the rumen samples produced a total of 2,468,556 bacterial reads, 4,878,899 archaeal reads, 1,144,867 fungal reads, and 2,179,805 protozoal reads. For each data set, one sample was excluded due to low sequencing depth, leaving 112 samples for downstream analysis. In total, 2478 bacterial, 105 archaeal, 69 fungal, and 103 protozoal ASV were identified.

Statistical analysis

The first 2 wk of each treatment period were assumed to be the adaptation period and were omitted from the data set. Statistical analysis of the performance variables, CH₄ emissions, and fermentation characteristics was performed using the statistical software program R (version, 4.4.2, www.r-project.org) and analyzed using a linear mixed model:

$$Y_{ijk} = D_i + T_j + (DT)_{ij} + P_k + C_l + \epsilon_{ijk},$$

where Y_{ijk} is the dependent variable; D_i is the fixed effect of the *i*th diet (*i* = GS, CS), T_j is the fixed effect of the *j*th treatment (*j* = CTRL, EL), $(DT)_{ij}$ is the interaction effect of the *i*th diet with the *j*th treatment; P_k is the fixed effect of the *k*th period (*k* = treatment period 1, treatment period 2, treatment period 3); C_l is the random effect of cow, and ϵ_{ijk} is the residual error. The results are presented as LSM per diet and treatment. *P*-values for the fixed effects were obtained from the *F*-tests of the linear mixed model. Differences were considered significant at $P \leq 0.05$ and a trend was considered as $0.05 < P \leq 0.1$.

When an interaction was observed, a Tukey post hoc test was performed to determine the differences between the 4 different dietary treatments. The analyzed outcomes of the performance variables, CH₄ emissions, and fermentation characteristics were assumed to be sufficiently normally distributed based on the graphical evaluation of the residuals of the models used (histogram and QQ-plot).

RESULTS

Nutrient intake

Cows fed the GS-based diet had a lower CP intake (3.25 vs. 3.58 kg DM/d) and a higher crude fiber intake (4.75 vs. 4.57 kg DM/d) and crude ash intake (1.81 vs. 1.48 kg DM/d) compared with those fed the CS-based diet ($P < 0.001$) (Table 3). Addition of EL increased crude fat intake (+325 g/d, $P < 0.001$) and decreased fermentable OM (FOM) intake (−765 g/d, $P < 0.001$) and crude ash intake (−200 g/d, $P < 0.001$), irrespective of the diet. Cows fed the CS-based diet had a higher intake of starch (5.06 vs. 3.68 kg DM/d, $P < 0.001$), MP (2.27 vs 2.07 kg DM/d, $P < 0.001$), and RDPB (−6 vs −69, $P < 0.001$) and a lower intake of sugar (0.85 vs 1.12 kg DM/d, $P < 0.001$) compared with the GS-based diet. The EL treatment reduced the intake of starch (−0.21 kg/d, $P < 0.001$), RDPB (−69 g/d, $P < 0.001$) and sugar (−0.09 kg/d, $P < 0.001$) and increased the MP intake (+110 g/d, $P < 0.001$).

Animal performance

Roughage DMI was 1.3 kg/d lower ($P < 0.001$) for cows on the GS diet compared with cows fed the CS-based diet (Table 3). Addition of EL resulted in a decrease ($P < 0.001$) of 0.9 kg/d in DMI of concentrates, consistent with the experimental design based on isoenergetic diets. Milk yield and FPCM were, 2.1 kg/d and 1.8 kg/d higher ($P < 0.001$) in cows fed the CS-based diet compared with the GS-based diet (Table 4). The addition of EL increased milk yield with 1.2 kg/d and FPCM with 1.1 kg/d. Milk protein content and MUN were higher ($P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.001$) when the CS-based diet was fed compared with cows on the GS-based diet (+0.10% points and +41 mg/L), but decreased ($P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.01$) with EL supplementation (−0.11% points and −7.5 mg/L, respectively). Milk fat content was higher ($P = 0.02$) in the cows on the GS-based diet (4.62%) than on the CS-based diet (4.56%). However, EL supplementation led to a reduction ($P = 0.01$) in milk fat content only when added to the GS-based diet (−0.14% points, *P*-value diet x treatment = 0.10). Additionally, EL supplementation increased lactose content (+0.06% points, $P < 0.001$).

Enteric methane emissions

Overall, CH₄ emissions (Table 5) were lower when cows were fed the CS-based diet compared with the GS-based diet, with reductions of 5.4%, 7.2%, 8.0%, and 11.9% in absolute CH₄ production (g/d, $P < 0.001$), CH₄ yield (g/kg DMI, $P < 0.006$), CH₄ intensity (g/kg MP, $P < 0.001$ and g/kg FPCM, $P < 0.001$). Addition of EL resulted in a reduction of 4.2%, 7.5% and 7.3% for CH₄ production ($P < 0.001$), CH₄ intensity (g/kg MY, $P < 0.001$ and g/kg FPCM, $P < 0.001$) irrespective of diet composition. The percentage of GEI lost as CH₄ increased 7.9% ($P = 0.01$) when CS was replaced by GS. Furthermore, CO₂ emissions (kg/d) were lower ($P = 0.03$) in the GS-based diet (14.2 kg/d) compared with the CS-based diet (14.4 kg/d). The addition of EL resulted in a reduced ($P < 0.01$) CO₂ production compared with the CTRL treatment (14.6 vs. 14.1 kg/d).

Ruminal VFA

Ruminal pH and total VFA concentration were not affected by diet, treatment, or an interaction between both (Table 5). The rumen fluid derived from cows on the GS-based diet showed a higher proportion of acetate

(+1.4% points; $P = 0.001$), butyrate (+1.1% points, $P < 0.001$), and a higher acetate-to-propionate ratio (+0.55, $P < 0.001$) and a lower proportion of propionate (−1.9% points, $P < 0.001$), valerate (−0.11% points, $P < 0.001$) and caproate (−0.06% points, $P < 0.01$). For butyrate, a trend for a diet × treatment interaction ($P = 0.070$) could be observed, where EL supplementation reduced butyrate proportion in cows on the GS diet (−0.6% points, $P < 0.05$), while no significant change was observed when cows were fed the CS-based diet. Iso-valerate proportion showed a significant diet × treatment interaction ($P = 0.027$): EL supplementation increased iso-valerate with 0.05% points in the CS-based diet, but decreased its proportion in the rumen fluid of cows fed with the GS-based diet with 0.05% points.

Meta-taxonomical analysis of ruminal microbiota

Relative abundance of the top 10 bacterial genera and the top 5 archaeal, fungal, and protozoal genera is shown in the supplementary materials (see supplementary Figure S2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17596939>). Cows fed the CS-based diet showed lower α diversity compared with those fed the GS-based diet, as reflected by reduced observed ASV, Shannon, and Simpson indices (Table 6).

Table 3. LSM of DMI (kg/d) and nutrient intake (kg/d, unless stated otherwise) of the different dietary treatments

	Dietary treatments ¹				SEM ²	P-value ³		
	CS		GS			Diet	Treatment	Diet*treatment
	CTRL	EL	CTRL	EL				
Total DMI	24.2	23.8	23.8	23.0	0.41	0.24	<0.01	0.23
DMI roughage	16.8	17.4	15.8	15.8	0.39	<0.001	0.89	0.15
DMI concentrates ⁴	6.8	5.8	7.5	6.5	0.10	<0.001	<0.001	0.87
CP	3.58	3.58	3.28	3.22	0.060	<0.001	0.15	0.31
Crude ash	1.58	1.38	1.93	1.70	0.026	<0.001	<0.001	0.34
Crude fat	0.62	0.95	0.64	0.96	0.011	0.14	<0.001	0.85
Crude fiber	4.56	4.57	4.81	4.69	0.094	<0.001	0.08	0.17
NDF	8.26	8.23	8.48	8.23	0.165	0.06	0.04	0.17
Starch	5.14	4.98	3.81	3.56	0.078	<0.001	<0.001	0.33
Sugar	0.89	0.81	1.16	1.07	0.016	<0.001	<0.001	0.93
NE _L ⁵ (MJ/d)	162	167	160	162	2.6	0.26	0.32	0.28
MP ⁶	2.21	2.34	2.02	2.11	0.037	<0.001	<0.001	0.38
RDPB ⁷ (g/d)	29	−40	−36	−105	3.9	<0.001	<0.001	0.97
FOM	14.05	13.44	14.01	13.09	0.229	0.82	<0.001	0.21
GE ⁸ (MJ/d)	439	443	426	421	7.4	0.02	0.37	0.24

¹Different dietary treatments with PMR: CS = corn silage-based diet (CS:GS of 75:25), GS = grass silage-based diet (CS:GS of 25:75), and treatments within each diet: CTRL = control treatment, EL = EL replacing a part of the balanced concentrates from the CTRL treatment.

²Highest value of SEM is published in the table.

³P-values for the fixed effects were obtained from the F-tests of the linear mixed model. Effects were considered significant at $P < 0.05$ and as showing a tendency when $0.05 \leq P < 0.10$.

⁴Concentrates included in the PMR, fed at the automated feeders, the milking parlor and used as bait in the GreenFeed system (formulated with a composition of 50% balanced concentrate blend and 50% starch-based concentrate).

⁵Net energy for lactation (MJ/d), Van Es, 1978.

⁶Metabolizable protein, Tamminga et al., 2007.

⁷Rumen degradable protein balance, Tamminga et al., 2007.

⁸Gross energy, calculated as $0.02414 \times \text{CP} + 0.03657 \times \text{Crude fat} + 0.02092 \times \text{Crude Fiber} + 0.01699 \times \text{NFC} - 0.00063 \times \text{Sugar}$ (Van Es, 1978).

For the protozoal community, only observed ASV was affected by diet ($P < 0.001$), with a lower diversity in the cows fed the CS-based diet (44–45) compared with the GS-based diet (48–49). For the archaeal community, both the Shannon and Simpson index showed an interaction effect ($P < 0.01$ and $P = 0.02$ respectively), with a decrease in these indices when EL was supplemented to cows fed the CS-based diet, with no significant effect in cows on the GS-based diet. PERMANOVA analysis indicated that both diet and EL supplementation had an influence on the bacterial ($P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.01$) and archaeal ($P < 0.01$ and $P = 0.02$) community structure (Figure 3). The Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrix of the fungal and protozoal community were affected by diet alone ($P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$). Overall, diet and EL supplementation explained only a small proportion of the total variance, as indicated by low R^2 values across microbial groups (bacteria: 0.05 and 0.02; archaea: 0.025 and 0.013; fungi: 0.095; protozoa: 0.030). Abundance of the bacterial genera *Succiniclasticum*, *UBA2810* (Family: *Succinivibrionaceae*), *Prevotella*, *UBA1258* (Family: *Lachnospiraceae*), and *bifidobacterium* were more abundant in the CS-based diet (Figure 4). In the fungal community, increased relative abundance of *NY05* (order of *Neocallimastigales*) was observed in the CS-based diet compared with the GS-based diet. On the other hand, the relative abundance of protozoal genera *Isotricha*, *Dasytrichia*, and *Entodinium* was lower in the cows fed on CS-based diet compared with the GS-based diet. In response to EL supplementation, 4 bacterial genera were

differentially abundant: *Limivacinus*, *RUG420* (Family: *Acetivibrionaceae*) and an unclassified ASV belonging to family: *Oscillospiraceae* increased. For the archaeal community an interaction effect was observed, showed that the addition of EL to the CS-based resulted in a decreased abundance of the genus *Methanicrooccus* as indicated by a negative log₂FC value compared with the addition of EL to the GS-based diet.

Quantitative PCR analysis of ruminal microbiota

The results indicate that neither diet, treatment, nor their interaction had a significant effect on microbial gene copy numbers ($P > 0.05$, Table 7).

DISCUSSION

This study investigated whether the effectiveness of EL as mitigation strategy is influenced by type of basal diet, specifically comparing a CS- and GS-based diets. Linseed-derived FA have been shown to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions in ruminants, though results on forage-type interactions are inconsistent (Benchaar et al., 2015; Van Mullem et al., 2025). The findings of this study do not indicate any interaction effect between the mitigating effect of EL and the composition of the basal diet. Therefore, the difference between the CS- and the GS-based diet and the effect of EL are discussed separately.

Table 4. LSM of production of milk and FPCM (kg/d), milk composition (fat (% and kg/d), protein (% and kg/d), lactose (% and kg/d) and MUN (mg/kg)

	Dietary treatments ¹				SEM ²	P-values ³		
	CS		GS			Diet	Treatment	Diet*treatment
	CTRL	EL	CTRL	EL				
Milk yield (kg/d)	32.6	33.5	30.2	31.7	0.82	<0.001	<0.001	0.24
FPCM yield (kg/d) ⁴	35.0	35.9	32.6	33.8	0.80	<0.001	<0.01	0.54
Feed efficiency ⁵	1.46	1.52	1.37	1.47	0.028	<0.001	<0.001	0.34
Milk composition								
Fat (%)	4.56	4.55	4.69	4.55	0.087	0.02	0.01	0.10
Protein (%)	3.73	3.62	3.63	3.52	0.049	<0.001	<0.001	0.89
Lactose (%)	4.80	4.85	4.79	4.85	0.029	0.56	<0.001	0.69
MUN (mg/kg)	113	105	72	65	2.6	<0.001	<0.01	0.88
Fat (kg/d)	1.47	1.51	1.39	1.43	0.038	<0.001	0.06	0.98
Protein (kg/d)	1.19	1.20	1.08	1.10	0.024	<0.001	0.12	0.28
Lactose (kg/d)	1.55	1.61	1.43	1.54	0.041	<0.001	<0.001	0.17

¹Different dietary treatments with PMR: CS = corn silage-based diet (CS:GS of 75:25), GS = grass silage-based diet (CS:GS of 25:75), and treatments within each diet: CTRL = control treatment, EL = EL replacing a part of the balanced concentrates from the CTRL treatment.

²Highest value of SEM is published in the table.

³P-values for the fixed effects were obtained from the F-tests of the linear mixed model. Effects were considered significant at $P < 0.05$ and as showing a tendency when $0.05 \leq P < 0.10$.

⁴Fat- and protein-corrected milk yield, calculated as FPCM yield = milk yield (kg/d) × [0.337 + (0.116 × milk fat%) + (0.06 × milk protein%)].

⁵Calculated as kilograms of FPCM yield per kilogram of DMI.

Table 5. LSM of CH₄ emissions (g/day, g/kg DMI, g/kg MP, g/kg FPCM and as % of GEI), CO₂ emissions (kg/d), pH, total VFA concentration (μmol/mol), and molar proportions (%) of individual VFA

	Dietary treatments ¹				SEM ²	P-values ³		
	CS		GS			Diet	Treatment	Diet*treatment
	CTRL	EL	CTRL	EL				
CH ₄ emissions								
g/d	520	491	547	522	11.4	<0.001	<0.001	0.702
g/kg DMI	21.6	20.7	22.9	22.8	0.44	0.01	0.91	0.17
g/kg milk	16.2	15.0	17.5	16.2	0.40	<0.001	<0.001	0.70
g/kg FPCM	14.9	13.8	16.7	15.8	0.44	<0.001	0.002	0.72
%GEI	6.65	6.32	7.07	6.92	0.148	0.01	0.34	0.41
CO ₂ emissions (kg/d)	14.7	14.1	14.4	14.0	0.21	0.03	<0.01	0.25
pH	6.91	6.91	6.89	6.89	0.038	0.63	0.90	0.98
Total VFA	101	102	98	100	3.4	0.59	0.65	0.95
Molar proportions								
Acetate	67.7	67.5	68.9	69.1	3.18	0.001	0.58	0.47
Propionate	17.1	17.3	15.1	15.5	3.29	<0.001	0.22	0.51
Butyrate	12.1	12.1	13.2	12.6	1.84	<0.001	<0.01	0.07
Isobutyrate	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.01	0.68	0.18	0.13
Valerate	1.0	1.1	0.9	0.9	0.02	<0.001	0.68	0.52
Isovalerate	1.0 ^a	1.0 ^a	0.8 ^b	0.8 ^b	0.03	<0.001	0.12	0.03
Caproate	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.01	<0.01	0.40	0.44
Acetate:Propionate	4.01	3.98	4.59	4.49	0.09	<0.001	0.31	0.62

¹Different dietary treatments with PMR: CS = corn silage-based diet (CS:GS of 75:25), GS = grass silage-based diet (CS:GS of 25:75), and treatments within each diet: CTRL = control treatment, EL = EL replacing a part of the balanced concentrates from the CTRL treatment.

²Highest value of SEM is published in the table.

³P-values for the fixed effects were obtained from the F-tests of the linear mixed model. Effects were considered significant at $P < 0.05$ and as showing a tendency when $0.05 \leq P < 0.10$.

Difference between CS based diet and GS based diet

Diets lower in starch are known to result in higher CH₄ emissions compared with diets high in starch levels (Eugène et al., 2021; Beauchemin et al., 2022). Consistent with this, the GS-based diet increased CH₄ emissions in comparison with the CS-based diet, which aligns with previous studies (Brask et al., 2013; van Gastelen et al., 2015, 2023). The reduced emissions from cows fed the CS-based diet were associated with higher molar proportion of propionate and a lower acetate-to-propionate ratio, similar as in Deusch et al. (2017). This higher proportion of propionate creates a H₂-limited environment with less substrate available for methanogenesis (Moss et al., 2000; Ungerfeld, 2020). These fermentation shifts were accompanied by shifts in the microbial community. The relative abundance of *Prevotella spp.*, *Succinivibrionaceae* (UBA2810) and *Succiniclasticum* were increased in cows fed the CS-based diet. These genera are associated with succinate and propionate metabolism (van Gylswyk, 1995; Purushe et al., 2010), supporting the activation of alternative H₂-utilization pathways other than methanogenesis. Concurrently, the CS-based diet led to a reduced relative abundance of protozoal genera such as *Entodinium*, *Dasytricha*, and *Isotricha*, which are known to contribute to H₂ and butyrate production (Lettat et al., 2013; Andersen et al., 2023). The reduced butyrate pro-

portion under the CS-based diet further supports a shift away from H₂ generating fermentation. Their reduction may have further limited H₂ availability for methanogenesis. Together, these microbial and metabolic patterns confirm that the CS-based diet creates an environment with more limited H₂ availability and lower CH₄ production potential compared with the GS-based diet.

Beyond its effect on fermentation patterns, the GS-based diet negatively affected milk yield. Combined with the increased CH₄ production, this resulted in a 13.2% increase in CH₄ intensity (g CH₄/kg FPCM). While previous studies linked this to a lower DMI under GS-based diets (Kliem et al., 2008; Hart et al., 2015; Livingstone et al., 2015), DMI in our study was not affected, indicating that other factors played a role. A likely explanation is the higher CP intake in the CS-based diet (3.62 vs. 3.28 kg/d), as also reported by van Gastelen et al. (2023). Increased CP levels have been associated with an increased milk output, with Colmenero and Broderick (2006) reporting a 2.0 kg/d increase when dietary CP rose from 13.5% to 16.5%. In our study, a comparable effect was observed: cows on the CS-based diet (15.1% CP) produced 2.4 kg/d more milk than those on the GS-based diet (13.9% CP). Furthermore, both diets were formulated to be iso-energetic, and no significant differences in FOM were detected. Still, the CS-based diet offered more fermentable energy in the form of starch and a

better supply of MP both key drivers of milk production (Hristov et al., 2004).

Furthermore, microbial diversity analyses support the hypothesized differences between CS and GS-based diets. Alpha diversity of bacteria, archaea, and fungi was significantly lower in cows fed the CS-based diet, whereas the protozoal community remained unaffected. This reduction in microbial richness aligns with reports that starch-rich diets can reduce microbial diversity (Belanche et al., 2012), whereas fiber-rich, forage based diets tend to support a more stable and diverse microbial community (Lettat et al., 2013; Vaidya et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2021). Within the protozoal community, specific taxa exhibited differential responses. Notably, *Entodinium caudatum*, a species associated with increased CH₄ emissions (Ranilla et al., 2007), declined under the CS-based diet, which may have contributed to the observed reduction in CH₄ production. However, the observed differences in microbial composition between diets are rather limited, as also shown by the small proportion of variation in the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity explained by diet (2.5–9.5%). These minor changes in microbial community composition contrasts with studies under lower forage-to-concentrate ratios (Deusch et al., 2017) and supports the idea that higher forage-to-concentrate ratios buffer microbial changes (Wallace et al., 2015; Tapio et al., 2017). Altogether, despite measurable effects of diet on microbial structure, the magnitude of these changes remained minimal under forage-rich conditions, under-

lining the resilience and functional redundancy of the rumen microbiota (Weimer, 2015; Lengowski et al., 2016).

Mitigating potential of EL

Diet-induced variations in rumen conditions did not modify the CH₄-mitigating effect of EL. The supplementation of EL reduced absolute CH₄ emissions by 4.8%, consistently across diets differing in starch content (21% vs. 16%). This reduction with 83 g/kg EL (+1.45% fat) aligns with the lower end of reduction of 6.1% in CH₄ production reported by Martin et al. (2016) for 70 g/kg EL in a CS diets. Similar fat increases (+1.32% to 1.6%) in a GS and CS diet, resulted either in no significant reduction in dairy heifers (Hammond et al., 2014) and a trend for a reduction of 7% in a CS-based diet in dairy cows (Van Mullem et al., 2025) in CH₄ production.

While linolenic acid has been shown to exert toxic effects on cellulolytic bacteria and protozoa in vitro (Maia et al., 2010; McKain et al., 2010), our results suggest that, at the inclusion level used here (+1.45% crude fat), the in vivo impact on the rumen microbiota was less pronounced. Similarly, several studies have reported no effect on cellulolytic bacteria or protozoa and only minor reductions in bacterial richness (Popova et al., 2011 (+1.9% crude fat), 2019 (+2.6% crude fat); Veneman et al., 2015 (+1.5% crude fat)), while others, in line with our results, observed no changes in fungal diversity based on the Shannon index (Boots et al., 2013 (+6% soybean oil);

Table 6. LSM of α diversity indices (observed ASV, Shannon index, and Simpson index) of rumen bacterial, fungal, protozoal, and archaeal communities

	Dietary treatments ¹				SEM ¹	P-values ²		
	CS		GS			Diet	Treatment	Diet*Treatment
	CTRL	EL	CTRL	EL				
Bacteria								
Observed ASV	394	425	412	418	12.6	0.18	0.66	0.19
Shannon index	5.22	5.28	5.35	5.35	0.040	<0.01	0.83	0.31
Simpson index	0.987	0.988	0.991	0.991	0.0012	<0.001	0.99	0.51
Archaea								
Observed ASV	48	44	51	49	1.0	0.01	<0.001	0.18
Shannon index	2.75 ^b	2.63 ^a	2.82 ^{bc}	2.82 ^c	0.038	0.01	<0.001	0.01
Simpson index	0.898 ^b	0.888 ^a	0.904 ^{bc}	0.907 ^c	0.0045	0.08	0.01	0.01
Fungi								
Observed ASV	25	25	26	27	0.9	0.02	0.16	0.26
Shannon index	2.71	2.70	2.92	2.92	0.025	<0.001	0.63	0.67
Simpson index	0.911	0.910	0.934	0.933	0.0030	<0.001	0.56	0.82
Protozoa								
Observed ASV	44	45	48	49	2.0	<0.001	0.38	0.72
Shannon index	2.87	2.86	2.94	2.94	0.076	0.27	0.88	0.87
Simpson index	0.908	0.910	0.915	0.908	0.0103	0.59	0.92	0.65

^{a-c}LSM values in the same row with different subscripts differ ($P < 0.05$) for the interaction between diet and treatment.

¹Different dietary treatments with PMR: CS = corn silage-based diet (CS:GS of 75:25), GS = grass silage-based diet (CS:GS of 25:75), and treatments within each diet: CTRL = control treatment, EL = EL replacing a part of the balanced concentrates from the CTRL treatment.

²P-values for the fixed effects were obtained from the F-tests of the linear mixed model. Effects were considered significant at $P < 0.05$ and as showing a tendency when $0.05 \leq P < 0.10$.

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Figure 3. NMDS plots of the Bray-Curtis distance of the bacterial, archaeal, fungal, and protozoal community of the 4 dietary treatments, analyzed at ASV level: CS CTRL (●), CS EL (●), GS CTRL (●), and GS EL (●). Each dot represents the microbial community of sample of an individual cow (3 samples per cow: 1 in each treatment period). Ellipses indicate the 95% CI for each dietary treatment.

Tapio et al., 2017 (+5% sunflower oil). Although sampling time of these studies was different, this probably have very little impact on the community structure (Jeyanathan et al., 2011; Belanche et al., 2012). Nevertheless, negative effects could be observed at higher inclusion levels. For instance, Martin et al. (2016) observed linear decreases in absolute abundance of protozoa with increasing amounts of EL in hay- and CS-based diets, while Huang et al. (2016) reported reduced bacterial diversity at 8.5% dietary fat from ground linseed. Despite the overall limited impact, differential abundance analysis showed shifts in the microbial communities. EL increased the relative abundance of 3 bacterial ASV

within order *Oscillospirales*, including *Limivacinus* and *RUG420*, and an unclassified genus.

In regard to the methanogens, *Methanimicrococcus*, a H_2 -dependent methylotrophic archaeal genus (Thomas et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2024), was significantly reduced by EL in the CS-based diet compared with EL in the GS-based diet. The hydrogenotrophic methanogens may be under pressure, as the ruminal conditions in the CS-based diet already have a lower H_2 availability (Ungerfeld, 2020). However, results suggest that methylotrophic methanogens were more affected. This aligns with findings by Saro et al. (2018), who observed reduced abundance of *Methanomassiliicoccaceae*, also a H_2 -dependent methy-

Figure 4. Results of differential abundance analysis. (A) shows the differentially abundant taxa of the MS diet VS GS diet, (B) shows the differentially abundant taxa of the EL treatment vs the CTRL treatment, and (C) represent the differentially abundant taxa of the EL treatment in the CS diet vs the EL treatment in the GS diet (interaction term). Differential abundance analysis was performed on ASV level. Taxa with an adjusted P-value <0.05 were included in this figure. The base mean was log-transformed (Log10 base mean) for better visualization. Log2 fold changes (Log2FC) indicate the differential abundance of the specific taxa, where a positive (green) log2FC indicates a higher abundance, and a negative log2FC (red) indicates a lower abundance.

lotrophic archaea, and lower CH₄ emissions following linseed-based supplementation (1.6 mL/kg BW linseed oil).

These rather limited microbial shifts are consistent with the rather limited CH₄ reduction observed in this study, further supporting that EL at moderate inclusion levels as

used in this study (+1.45% crude fat) causes only limited disruption to the rumen microbiota. Despite the expectation that EL supplementation could disrupt cellulolytic bacteria and protozoa, leading to shifts in fermentation patterns toward higher propionate proportions (Johnson and Johnson, 1995; Beauchemin et al., 2022), our results show only minor microbial changes. The limited impact of EL on the rumen microbiota, particularly on cellulolytic bacteria and protozoa, is reflected in the absence of significant shifts in VFA profiles, with propionate and other major VFA remaining largely unchanged. These results suggest that, at the relatively low yet practically feasible inclusion level applied here, the modest reduction in absolute CH₄ production is mainly due to a decreased intake of fermentable OM rather than shifts in fermentation pathways. Furthermore, it is unlikely that other observed differences were linked to changes in rumen metabolism. Although total DMI was lower in cows supplemented with EL, this reduction was not caused by EL itself, but was a direct consequence of the experimental design. Specifically, 3.0 kg DM/d of balanced concentrates was replaced by 1.9 kg DM/d of EL to maintain iso-energetic treatments. Despite ad libitum access to the PMR, the cows did not fully compensate for this difference by increasing their PMR intake. Additionally, reductions in DMI are typically observed only when EL provides more than 600g of fat/cow/d, which was not the case in the present study (321 g/d) (Meignan et al., 2017).

Although DMI was lower, milk production was increased when EL was supplemented. Despite the diets being formulated to be iso-energetic, actual NE_L intake was numerically higher in EL-fed cows: +3.5 MJ. Theoretically, the additional energy could support 1.1 kg more FPCM, assuming 3.18 MJ are required per kg of FPCM, which closely matched the observed increase of 1.05 kg. As a result, EL supplementation led to an average reduction in CH₄ intensity of 7.4% per kg of milk and 7.3% per

kg of FPCM. However, earlier reported effects of EL on milk yield vary: some studies observed increases (Hurtaud et al., 2010; Graulet et al., 2019), others decreases (Chilliard et al., 2009), or no effect (van Zijderveld et al., 2011; Livingstone et al., 2015; Martin et al., 2016). As such, the increase in milk yield appears to be a consequence of the (numerically) higher NE_L content of the EL-supplemented diet rather than a direct milk-promoting effect of EL itself. The milk fat content showed a trend ($P = 0.01$) toward being affected by the interaction between the diet and EL supplementation, with a greater numerical reduction in the GS diet (−0.14% points) compared with the MS diet (−0.01% points). High starch levels, low dietary fiber and UFA are known risk factors for milk fat depression (Chilliard et al., 2009; Rico et al., 2015). Based on earlier studies, a stronger reduction in milk fat would be expected in the MS diet due to its greater susceptibility to milk fat depression (Ferlay et al., 2013; Meignan et al., 2017). De novo FA synthesis is inhibited by trans-isomers (mainly trans-10 C18-FA) produced during biohydrogenation (Baumgard et al., 2000; Chilliard et al., 2001; Shingfield et al., 2010). EL supplementation alters rumen fermentation resulting in increased production of trans-10 C18:1 (Hurtaud et al., 2010) and even more trans-10 C18:1 is more produced when a diet contains more CS (Meignan et al., 2017). On the other hand, Lerch et al. (2012) indicated a dilution effect of EL on milk fat. In our study, this also could have been the case as the addition of EL resulted in an larger increase in milk production, and hence, potentially more dilution in the GS diet (+1.5kg/d) than the CS diet (+0.9kg/d). Furthermore, the fat production (kg/d) showed no significant interaction effect between the diet and the addition of EL, supporting this dilution effect.

Table 7. LSM of rumen microbial gene copy numbers determined by quantitative PCR in rumen fluid

	Dietary treatments ¹				SEM ²	P-values ³		
	CS		GS			Diet	Treatment	Diet*Treatment
	CTRL	EL	CTRL	EL				
Bacteria	11.0	11.0	11.0	10.9	0.06	0.52	0.77	0.64
Archaea	10.4	10.4	10.4	10.3	0.07	0.19	0.51	0.32
Fungi	8.9	8.9	8.8	8.7	0.08	0.14	0.68	0.95
Protozoa	9.3	9.2	9.3	9.3	0.03	0.78	0.65	0.76

¹Different dietary treatments with PMR: CS = corn silage-based diet (CS:GS of 75:25), GS = grass silage-based diet (CS:GS of 25:75), and treatments within each diet: CTRL = control treatment, EL = EL replacing a part of the balanced concentrates from the CTRL treatment.

²Highest value of SEM is published in the table.

³P-values for the fixed effects were obtained from the F-tests of the linear mixed model. Effects were considered significant at $P < 0.05$ and as showing a tendency when $0.05 \leq P < 0.10$.

The lack of an interaction

The results of this study showed that the GS-based diet led to ruminal conditions characterized by a shift in the fermentation pattern and microbial community toward reduced propionate production. This outcome was consistent with our expectations and based on stoichiometric relations between VFA proportions and CH₄ production, indicates an increased H₂ pool under these conditions (Janssen, 2010; Ungerfeld, 2020). These differences were hypothesized to influence the effectiveness of EL. However, the results of this study did not show any interaction effects between the diet and the effectiveness of EL, which contrasted with our expectations. For direct inhibitors of rumen methanogenesis (e.g., 3-NOP, bromoform), it has been suggested that diets lower in starch and higher in NDF lead to a larger H₂ pool and a greater abundance of methanogens (Kebreab et al., 2023, 2025). As these inhibitors achieve a similar absolute reduction in CH₄ formation under both high-starch and high-NDF conditions, the higher baseline CH₄ production in high-NDF diets results in a smaller relative reduction in emissions (Kebreab et al., 2023, 2025). However, in the present study, EL supplementation provoked no or only minor changes in the bacterial or archaeal communities. Also, only a limited decrease in CH₄ was observed, most likely due to the reduction in FOM rather than to a direct effect direct microbial or fermentation-altering effect. Hence, in such situations with relatively small and non-microbially driven effects, the absence of an interaction effect may not be surprising. It is possible that at higher fat levels and/or with more potent fat sources (e.g., oil instead of EL), and under diets with a higher forage-to-concentrate ratio, an interaction could occur.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that supplementation of EL reduced absolute CH₄ emissions in dairy cows with 4.8%, regardless of the basal diet being CS or GS based. Although the GS-based diet resulted in a higher H₂ availability and microbial richness, these changes did not affect the CH₄-mitigating potential of EL. At the inclusion level used, EL had only minor effects on rumen microbiota and fermentation patterns, which is reflected in the absence of significant shifts in VFA profiles. The reduction in CH₄ production was largely driven by a reduced intake of FOM rather than microbial or metabolic changes. Although concentrates were replaced on an isoenergetic basis, EL supplementation increased milk yield because the diet provided numerically more net energy. Overall, these findings indicate that this dose of EL can be effectively used as a CH₄ mitigation strategy in diets

differing in forage type without adversely affecting rumen fermentation or milk composition.

Notes

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During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT in the writing process to improve readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

The authors have not stated any conflicts of interest to disclose.

Abbreviations: ASV = amplicon sequence variant, CS = corn silage, EL = extruded linseed, FA = fatty acids, FOM = fermentable organic matter, FPCM = fat- and protein corrected milk, GE = gross energy, GEI = gross energy intake, GS = grass silage, Log₂FC = Log₂ fold change, NMDS = nonmetric multidimensional scaling, PMR = partial mixed ratio, RDPB = rumen degradable protein balance.

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ORCID

J. Van Mullem, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3235-3276>

J. Jeyanathan, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6056-8162>

B. Ampe, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8223-2870>

N. Peiren, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5500-1607>

V. Fievez, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5042-6200>

L. Vandaele <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4563-6796>